

CPT-SPT Correlation of Volcanic Soils in Kediri, East Java

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ABSTRAK: Korelasi CPT-SPT merupakan salah satu korelasi yang paling umum dibuat dalam praktek geoteknik. Peneliti-peneliti telah mengusulkan korelasi tersebut untuk tanah kohesif maupun tanah granular. Namun demikian, korelasi untuk tanah khusus, misalnya tanah vulkanik, masih terbatas. Artikel ini membahas tentang korelasi CPT-SPT pada tanah vulkanik di Kediri, Jawa Timur. Uji Penetrasi Konus (CPT), yaitu dalam hal ini uji *piezocone* (CPTu), dilakukan secara berdampingan dengan Uji Penetrasi Standar (SPT). Tujuh belas pasang data CPTu dan SPT digunakan untuk membuat korelasi $q_t - N$ dan $f_s - N$. Korelasi $q_t - N$ memberikan hasil rasio $q_t/N = 2.15$ (q_t dalam satuan kg/cm^2) dengan koefisien determinasi R^2 sebesar 0.92. Korelasi ini cenderung mirip dengan korelasi untuk material lempung dan lempung kelanauan. Korelasi yang baik juga diperoleh untuk hubungan $f_s - N$, dimana dihasilkan rasio $f_s/N = 9$ (f_s dalam satuan kPa) dengan R^2 sebesar 0.88. Sebagai tambahan, nilai N -SPT terstandarisasi (N_{60}) diestimasi menggunakan korelasi antara indeks perilaku tanah (I_c) dari pengukuran CPTu dan nilai N -SPT yang diusulkan Lunne dkk. (1997) dan Robertson (2012). Hasil estimasi menunjukkan bahwa kedua korelasi memberikan nilai N_{60} terprediksi lebih rendah 20 hingga 49 persen daripada nilai N_{60} yang terukur di lapangan. Dengan demikian, sebuah korelasi baru diusulkan untuk jenis tanah spesifik ini dan didapati korelasi yang lebih baik.

Kata Kunci: Uji Penetrasi Konus (CPT), Uji Penetrasi Standar (SPT), korelasi, tanah vulkanik

ABSTRACT: CPT-SPT correlation is one of the most common correlations made in geotechnical practice. Researchers have been proposed such correlations for both cohesive and granular soils. However, correlations for a particular soil, for instance, volcanic soils, are still limited. This paper presents CPT-SPT correlations of volcanic soils in Kediri, East Java. Cone penetration tests, namely piezocone test (CPTu), were conducted side-by-side with Standard Penetration Test (SPT). Seventeen CPTu and SPT data pairs were mainly used to develop $q_t - N$ and $f_s - N$ correlations. The $q_t - N$ correlation results $q_t/N = 2.15$ (q_t in kg/cm^2) with a coefficient of determination R^2 of 0.92. This relationship tends to be similar to the same correlation for clay and silty clay materials. A good agreement is also obtained for the $f_s - N$ correlation, which resulted in $f_s/N = 9$ (f_s in kPa) with an R^2 of 0.88. Additionally, a standardized SPT N -value (N_{60}) is estimated using a relationship between soil behavior index (I_c) from the CPTu measurement and SPT N -value, suggested by Lunne et al. (1997) and Robertson (2012). Results show that both relationships give 22 to 49 percent lower predicted values of N_{60} compared to in-situ N_{60} values. A new correlation, thus, is proposed for this particular soil type, and a better agreement is obtained.

Keywords: Cone Penetration Test (CPT), Standard Penetration Test (SPT), correlation, volcanic soils

1 INTRODUCTION

Cone Penetration Test (CPT) and Standard Penetration Test (SPT) are two in-situ tests most used globally, including Indonesia. Their application in projects has become more

common since they were required by Indonesian National Standard (SNI), specifically SNI 8460:2017 (SNI, 2017) about Geotechnical Design Requirements. Additionally, many future projects, both scaled

locally and nationally, promote the usage of these tests even more.

The abundance of CPT and SPT data encourages researchers and practitioners to study and correlate these two test results for practical use. Many empirical CPT-SPT correlations for numerous soils have been proposed, including non-textbook materials, for example, residual and volcanic soils. In fact, in Indonesia, both practitioners and academicians often encounter these unique materials in projects. Nonetheless, it appears that even though the CPT and SPT data are plentiful, such correlations on these materials are still limited.

This paper attempts to provide reliable local CPT-SPT correlations for volcanic soils in Kediri. The relationship between the two tests was developed using high-quality field data. Therefore, the proposed correlations can be utilized maximally by practical engineers to evaluate and design various geotechnical works. Moreover, this study was also intended to suggest a new CPT-SPT correlation between $(q_t/p_a)/N_{60}$ and CPT-based SBT Index (I_c) for this specific soil type. The suggested correlation can then be used for predicting standardized N_{60} values using piezocone (CPTu) soundings.

2 PREVIOUS STUDIES OF CPT-SPT CORRELATION

Zhao and Cai (2013) noted that the study of CPT-SPT correlations could be broadly delineated into three categories:

1. Ratio method

In this method, the cone resistance of the CPT and the SPT N -value was assumed to have a simple linear relationship. Many researchers have proposed the ratio of q_c/N for various types of soils, including other materials such as volcanic soils. Table 1 and Table 2 recap some available $q_c - N$ correlations from the 1950s to 2000s. This method is prevalent because of its practicability and convenience since many geotechnical designs often use empirical correlations based on CPT and SPT. For instance, if the q_c data are present, they can be converted easily to SPT N -value or vice versa. The converted values are then can be used for the evaluation or design of geotechnical works. Nevertheless, it

should be noted that every soil type has different q_c/N ratios, and other materials may have unique ratios.

Table 1. Some Published $q_c - N$ Correlations

Soil Type	q_c/N (kg/cm ²)	References
Silts, sandy silts, slightly cohesive silt-sand mixtures	2	Schmertmann (1970)
Clay, silty clay, clayey silt	3.5	Velloso (1959)
	3	Sanglerat (1972)
	1.3	Kruizinga (1982)
Sandy clay and silty sand	2	Velloso (1959)
Sandy clay	4	Sanglerat (1972)
Sandy silt	3.5	Velloso (1959)
Clean, fine to medium sands and slightly silty sands	3 - 4	Schmertmann (1970)
Silty sand	5	Sanglerat (1972)
Coarse sands and sands with little gravel	5 - 6	Schmertmann (1970)
Clayey sand	6	Sanglerat (1972)
(Silty) fine sand	4	Meigh and Nixon (1961)
Fine sand	4	Meyerhof (1956)
	6	Velloso (1959)
Medium and coarse sand	8	Meigh and Nixon (1961)
Sand	10	Velloso (1959)
	4.5	Kruizinga (1982)
Sandy gravels and gravel	8 - 10	Schmertmann (1970)
Gravelly sand	12	Meigh and Nixon (1961)
Sandy gravel	12 - 16	Meigh and Nixon (1961)

Table 2. Available $q_c - N$ Correlations for Other Materials

Soil Type	q_c/N (kg/cm ²)	References
Pumice, volcanic ash, loam	8	Miura et al. (2003)
Alluvium silty sand, silt (volcanic soil deposits)	8.5	Takesue et al. (1996)
Silty sand (residual soil)	3.9	Costa et al. (2016)
Sandy estuarine sediment	2.2	Kantey (1965)
Chalk	3 - 7	Power (1982)

2. Function method

This method considers that the relation between q_c and SPT N -values is not linear. Some researchers suggested a more complicated function of these two parameters to increase the accuracy (Akca 2003; Kara and Gunduz 2010; Zhao and Cai 2013). This approach, however, did not consider the soil properties which may affect the CPT-SPT correlation. Moreover, a complicated mathematical expression is often less preferable to engineers because it includes time-consuming math operations.

3. Soil parameter method

One of the first CPT-SPT correlation studies that included soil properties was Robertson et al. (1983), which suggested the q_c/N ratio as a function of mean grain size (D_{50}). Ten years later, Jefferies and Davies (1993) discovered a new relationship between the q_c/N ratio and Soil Behavior Type (SBT) Index, I_c . They suggested that the most reliable way to obtain SPT N -values was to perform a CPT and convert them to an equivalent SPT. They proposed a method to convert the CPT cone resistance, q_t , to an equivalent SPT N -value at 60% energy, N_{60} , using Jefferies and Davies's Soil Behavior Type (SBT) index, I_{cJD} .

Jefferies and Davies (1993) method was then modified by Lunne et al. (1997), in which they used the I_c formulation from Robertson and Wride (1990) as follows:

$$I_c = [(3.47 - \log Q_t)^2 + (\log F_r + 1.22)^2]^{0.5} \quad (1)$$

where:

$$Q_t = \text{normalized cone resistance} \\ = (q_t - \sigma_{vo}) / \sigma_v'$$

$$F_r = \text{normalized friction ratio} \\ = f_s / (q_t - \sigma_{vo})$$

$$q_t = \text{corrected cone resistance} \\ = q_c + (1 - a) u_2;$$

$$a = \text{area ratio of the cone}$$

$$\sigma_{vo} = \text{overburden pressure (total)}$$

$$\sigma_v' = \text{overburden pressure (effective)}$$

Then, the CPT-SPT relationship they proposed can be expressed as:

$$(q_t/p_a)/N_{60} = 8.5 [1 - (I_c/4.6)] \quad (2)$$

Robertson (2012) reported that the above method had been shown to work effectively in a wide range of soils. However, recent experience in North America has shown that equation (1) tends to underpredict the N_{60} values in some clays. Hence, Robertson (2012) recommended an updated relationship that can be defined by an equation as follows:

$$(q_t/p_a)/N_{60} = 10^{(1.1268 - 0.2817 I_c)} \quad (3)$$

He added that the above equation produced a slightly larger N_{60} in fine-grained soils than the Jefferies and Davies (1993) method. In fine-grained soils with high sensitivity, equation (3) may overestimate the N_{60} .

3 CPT AND SPT METHODOLOGY

CPT and SPT data used in this research were collected from an airport project at Kediri, East Java. All test was carried out by the same company, and the same procedure was applied to all locations. The following subsection outlines the CPT and SPT methodology utilized for each testing point.

3.1 Cone Penetration Testing

The Cone Penetration Test (CPT) is a versatile and widely used method for geotechnical investigation. In the research site, the CPT conducted were all piezocone (CPTu) tests. In principle, the test is performed by pushing a piezocone into the soil with a constant pushing rate, following ASTM D5778 (ASTM, 2020). Fig. 1 shows the overview of CPT.

Fig. 1. Overview of the Cone Penetration Test (CPT) Per ASTM D 5778 Procedures (Mayne, 2007)

3.2 Standard Penetration Testing

The Standard Penetration Test (SPT) was performed following the ASTM D1586 (ASTM, 2018). The test drives a standard split spoon sampler into the soil/rock at a certain depth in a borehole. An automatic hammer of 63.5 kg weight falling freely from a height of 75 cm (30 inches) on the drill rod is used to drive the sampler. The number of hammer blows to drive the second and the third 15 cm of penetration is called the SPT N -value, representing the number of blows per 30 cm of penetration.

In order to calculate the standardized SPT N -value (N_{60}), the following equation is used:

$$N_{60} = N \times \left(\frac{ER}{60}\right) \times C_B \times C_S \times C_R \quad (4)$$

where:

N = field-measured blow count

ER = SPT hammer efficiency as determined by energy measurements in accordance with ASTM D4633 (ASTM, 2016)

C_B = correction factor for borehole diameter

C_S = correction factor for sampler geometry

C_R = correction factor for rod length

In this study, since the test was performed using the automatic hammer, the ER was taken 75. Other SPT correction factors such as borehole diameter, sampler geometry, and rod length were assumed to be 1.0.

4 DATA PROCESSING AND DEVELOPED CORRELATIONS

4.1 Data Processing

It is well known that the mechanism of CPT and SPT is different from one to another, especially regarding the measurement of resistance of the soils. In the CPT, the soil resistance is measured due to quasi-static penetration of the cone. On the other hand, SPT measures soil resistance based on dynamic force from a free-fall hammer transferred to the rod at a certain depth. Thus, to provide a comparable CPT and SPT measurement, the mean of each CPT variable (q_c , f_s , and I_c) was determined over the 300 mm length of each SPT. Averaging on the seating drive was excluded since the soil experienced high disturbance from the hammer blows. Fig. 2 visualizes the averaging method of the CPT variable.

Fig. 2. Calculation of CPT Parameters based on SPT Location (Wotherspoon et al. 2015)

There were more than 100 CPT and boreholes available on the research site, and these data undoubtedly provide valuable information for local correlations. However, not all of them can be utilized because there were differences in testing elevation and the distance between the tests was too far apart. Hence, to refine the datasets, the following filters were applied:

- CPT and SPT soundings used are only spaced equals or less than 10 m apart and with the same test elevations. The reason behind this is to reduce the effect of inhomogeneity.
- All incomplete SPT drive lengths were removed (i.e., those with less than 450 mm total penetration).
- SPT N -values higher than 20 were excluded since the specific CPT apparatus used in the field hardly penetrates this stratum.

Based on the above filters, a total of six CPT and SPT soundings were evaluated, resulting in 17 data pairs for correlations. The location of the tests is shown in Fig. 3. The majority of the testing points were located in the north area except for the CPT PCPT1-15 and borehole BH2-11.

The observed depths range from 1 to 14 m below the existing ground, with 12 data located above the groundwater level (GWL). As for the soil types, the identification was determined using the Unified Soil Classification System (USCS). Table 3 summarizes the filtered data used for developing correlations. It is clearly shown that silts are the most common soil type found on site.

Fig. 3. Borehole and Piezocone (CPTu) Locations

Table 3. Filtered Data for Correlations

BH No.	CPT No.	Depth (m)	Sample Location	Soil Type
BH6-37	PCPT1-32	6	Above GWL	ML
BH6-37	PCPT1-32	8	Above GWL	ML
BH6-36	PCPT2-48	2	Above GWL	SM
BH7-2	C2-8	2	Above GWL	MH
BH7-2	C2-8	4	Above GWL	MH
BH7-2	C2-8	6	Above GWL	ML
BH7-2	C2-8	12	Above GWL	CL
BH7-2	C2-8	14	Below GWL	CL
BH8-57	C2-9	7	Above GWL	ML
BH8-57	C2-9	9	Above GWL	ML
BH5-24	S-26	2	Above GWL	CH
BH5-24	S-26	4	Above GWL	MH
BH5-24	S-26	8	Below GWL	MH
BH2-11	PCPT1-15	1	Above GWL	ML
BH2-11	PCPT1-15	3	Above GWL	ML
BH2-11	PCPT1-15	5	Above GWL	CH
BH2-11	PCPT1-15	7	Above GWL	ML

4.2 Developed Correlations

As mentioned earlier in section 2, the study of CPT-SPT correlations can be divided into three categories: ratio method, function method, and soil parameter method. In this study, the proposed correlations focus on the first and the third method, considering the more practical

application. The ratio of cone resistance and SPT N-value (q_t/N) was developed based on a simple linear relationship with zero intercept. This approach is very logical and widely accepted by engineers and academicians. In addition to q_t/N , the same approach was applied to develop the ratio of sleeve friction to SPT N-value (f_s/N).

Furthermore, the CPT-SPT relationship in terms of Soil Behavior Type (SBT) Index, I_c , formulated by Robertson and Wride (1990), was suggested. Previous correlations from Lunne et al. (1997) and Robertson (2012) are used to evaluate their reliability to estimate N_{60} values of Kediri volcanic soils. Finally, this study aims to provide a local relationship between $(q_t/p_a)/N_{60}$ and I_c for this specific soil type.

5 SOIL AND GEOLOGICAL CONDITION

The ground condition can be assessed using in-situ test data and information from a local geological map. Rather than contradicting each other, these two pieces of information are more likely to complement. The CPT and SPT provide measured data and actual condition of the ground, while a geological map gives an idea of what geological layer is beneath the project location.

Fig. 4. Soil Condition from SPT and CPT Soundings

Fig. 5. Research Site on Geological Map of Madiun Quadrangle, Java (Map Data: Google, © 2021 Maxar Technologies; geological map reprinted from Hartono et al. 1992)

Drilling and SPT identified the surface layer as a cohesive stratum of clays and silts with medium to stiff consistency and a thickness of 2 to 3 meters. A hard layer was found at a depth of about 16 m below the existing ground level. This condition was also consistent with the CPT soundings. In addition, based on the collected samples, the cementation of materials was not present except for the hard consistency of the volcanic breccia layer. Fig. 4 depicts the typical soil stratification at the research site based on the CPT and SPT. The volcanic breccia stratum in this figure is not visible because it is located 30 m below the ground surface.

Information contained in the geological map is also beneficial for identifying the soil condition. Based on the geological map of Madiun Quadrangle (Hartono et al. 1992), the research site is located on the geological layer

of *Qp*, which consists of volcanic breccia, tuff, agglomerate, and lava. Therefore, it can be expected that the soils were volcanic soils and the weathering products of volcanic rocks.

6 ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

6.1 $q_t - N$ and $f_s - N$ Correlations

As presented earlier in the introduction section, numerous researchers have proposed q_c/N ratios for many soils, but only some researchers suggested f_s/N correlation (Kruzinga 1982; Takesue et al. 1996). In fact, for most soils, the SPT N -value is dominated by sampler side friction. Therefore, this study presents both correlations to provide options to geotechnical

engineers for design. Fig. 6 shows the obtained correlations for Kediri volcanic soils.

Fig. 6. $q_t - N$ and $f_s - N$ Correlations for Volcanic Soils in Kediri

Results show that a good agreement is obtained for both $q_t - N$, and $f_s - N$ correlations, in which the coefficient of determination (R^2) are 0.92 and 0.88, respectively. The q_t/N (in kg/cm^2) ratio is approximately 2.15, close to the ratio for cohesive silt-sand mixtures proposed by Schmertmann (1970). This correlation, however, is significantly different from the results obtained by Miura et al. (2003). The reason is that the Kediri volcanic soils are not cemented, and thus, the effect of particle crushing during SPT is not present. Moreover, the ratio of f_s/N (in kPa) is about 9, higher than quartz sands and alluvium silty sands and silts. These results were obtained since the soils are dominated by cohesive soils (clays and silts).

6.2 Estimation of N_{60} from CPTu

Based on the previous studies of Lunne et al. (1997) and Robertson (2012), this study examines whether their proposed correlations can be used for Kediri volcanic soils.

Equivalent N_{60} values were predicted using both methods to evaluate their reliability. Fig. 7 shows the comparison between measured N_{60} and N_{60} estimated by the two equations.

a) Based on Equation from Lunne et al. (1997)

b) Based on Equation from Robertson (2012)

Fig. 7. Prediction of N_{60} from CPT

The graphs show that the two equations underpredict the N_{60} by 49% for the Lunne et al. (1997) method and 22% for the Robertson (2012) method. Although it is better than the Lunne et al. (1997) method, estimation based on Robertson's method still depicts a scattered data, with most of them produces lower values of N_{60} . This result shows that the existing equations are less suitable for Kediri volcanic soils.

A graph was made with SBT Index (I_c) in the x -axis and the ratio of $(q_t/p_a)/N_{60}$ in the y -axis to develop a more accurate prediction of N_{60} . Measured data were then plotted into the graph, and a trendline was proposed. The suggested relationship is slightly modified from Robertson (2012), and it can be written as follows:

$$(q_t/p_a)/N_{60} = 10^{(1.1 - 0.32 I_c)} \quad (5)$$

Fig. 8 shows the proposed and previous CPT-SPT correlations, along with the Kediri volcanic soils data. Some ML soil type data points seem to be out of the flock because their $(q_t/p_a)/N_{60}$ equals or less than unity. Nevertheless, the above relationship represents the best fit line to the data.

Fig. 8. Proposed and Previous SPT-CPT Correlations in terms of $(q_t/p_a)/N_{60}$ and CPT-based SBT Index I_c

Estimation of N_{60} was performed once again using the proposed equation. The comparison of the predicted and the measured N_{60} can be seen in Fig. 9. The result showed that a good agreement was met, in which the estimated N_{60} was 7% higher than the measured data. Though scatters can still be recognized, for Kediri volcanic soils, the proposed relationship better predicts N_{60} values than two previous correlations.

Fig. 9. Prediction of N_{60} from CPT Based on the Proposed Equation

7 CONCLUSION SUMMARY

CPT – SPT correlation for volcanic soils of Kediri has been proposed, namely $q_t - N$ and $f_s - N$ correlation. Estimation of N_{60} from CPTu was also performed based on existing equations, and a specific equation for Kediri volcanic soils was suggested. The results of this study can be summarized as follows:

1. From 17 data pairs of CPT and SPT results, the ratio of q_t/N for Kediri volcanic soils is about 2.15 (in kg/cm^2), which is similar to clays and silt-like materials rather than volcanic-cemented soils in Japan (as reported by Miura et al. 2003). The reason is that the observed volcanic soils in Kediri are mainly uncemented silts and clays.
2. The f_s/N ratio (in kPa) was found around 9, higher than those of quartz sands and alluvium silty sand and silt reported by Takesue et al. (1996). Again, this finding is because those Kediri volcanic soils are predominantly clays and silts, and therefore, the sleeve resistance (f_s) is higher than those in sands.
3. Estimation of N_{60} from CPTu using existing equations from Lunne et al. (1997) and Robertson (2012) resulted in lower values of N_{60} compared to measured N_{60} , and thus, less suitable for practical application on Kediri volcanic soils. A new equation was suggested in a simpler expression, and it resulted in a better estimation of N_{60} with only 7% higher than the in-situ N_{60} values.

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